

MODERN INTERPRETATION OF CONCEPTS IN TEXTBOOKS TAUGHT IN PRIMARY GRADES AS A FACTOR IN DEVELOPING LOGICAL THINKING OF STUDENTS

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Abstract. *In this article, the modern interpretation of the concepts in the textbooks taught in primary grades, which are the basis for the development of logical thinking of students, has been developed from the scientific side. It has been revealed that one of the priorities of the day is to make wider use of the possibilities of National Qualifications Frameworks and Professional Standards.*

Keywords: *knowledge, logic, logical thinking, sensation, perception, imagination, understanding, judgment, conclusion, evidence, thinking, design, problem-based learning, teaching methodology, complex, general-systems theory, person-centered learning or scenario.*

Introduction

Modernizing the interpretation of concepts in primary education textbooks as a factor in developing students' logical thinking. In the Republic of Uzbekistan, one of the key priorities in the ongoing educational reforms is to make extensive use of National Qualification Frameworks (NQF) and Occupational Standards (OS) when organizing the educational process. At the same time, several regulatory documents have been adopted to enhance the quality of education and align higher education with global best practices:

- The Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PD-76, dated May 5, 2025, “On Additional Measures to Ensure the Quality of Education and Improve the Provision of Educational Services” [2].
- The Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 498, dated August 6, 2025, “On the Implementation of a System of Comprehensive and Specialized State Accreditation for Secondary Specialized, Vocational, Higher and Postgraduate Education, as well as Organizations for Retraining and Advanced Training of Personnel”.
- The Order of the Director of the National Agency for Education Quality Assurance under the Administration of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, approving indicators for assessing higher education programs in the framework of specialized state accreditation.

Definitely, these regulations aim to improve the competitiveness of national personnel and enhance the quality of the higher education system based on international standards. To achieve

this, indicators for assessing educational programs during state accreditation have been developed, targeting pressing issues for improving education quality.

Specifically, the regulations establish:

1. Systematic collection, analysis, and monitoring of data on labor market needs, educational requirements, and the latest trends in scientific research, with clearly defined tasks and functions for the relevant administrative structures.
2. Mechanisms to inform students about opportunities available in the labor market.
3. Development of educational programs in accordance with established procedures, ensuring that the objectives, outcomes, labor market requirements, OS, DTS (State Educational Standards), and NQF are met.
4. Involvement of employers, industry experts, and faculty members in the curriculum development process to ensure a systematic approach.
5. Transparency for the public, applicants, and students, allowing them to access accurate and impartial information about educational programs.
6. Alignment of curricula and study plans with NQF, DTS, occupational standards, qualification requirements, and/or international educational standards.
7. Application of advanced pedagogical technologies in the educational process to achieve appropriate effectiveness.
8. Regular use of new teaching methods and advanced pedagogical and innovative approaches (hereinafter referred to as “advanced pedagogical approaches”) in lessons.
9. Integration of advanced pedagogical approaches to deepen understanding of subject content, develop students’ independent learning, analytical, critical, creative thinking, and collaborative skills, while effectively achieving learning outcomes defined in the curriculum.
10. Updating study plans, curricula, and methodological materials based on monitoring and analysis results, along with the development and implementation of methodological manuals and teaching materials related to advanced pedagogical approaches.
11. Transparent and fair assessment of students’ knowledge, ensuring that evaluation procedures align with learning outcomes [4].

This scholarly article serves as a practical guide for implementing the above priority tasks, particularly in modernizing educational content in primary grades to develop students’ logical thinking and cognitive skills.

The Main Goal of Developing Students’ Logical Thinking

The primary aim of developing students’ logical thinking is to cultivate the skills of logical, consistent, and independent reasoning during the process of mastering mathematical knowledge, and to prepare them to make sound decisions in real-life situations. Through this, children acquire mental activities such as analysis, generalization, comparison, identifying cause-and-effect relationships, and drawing conclusions.

For developing the thinking abilities of primary school students through the teaching of key concepts, new curricula were gradually introduced starting from the 2024/2025 academic year according to the state program project. These curricula aim to educate students in humanistic and national values, patriotism, and to develop communication skills, critical and creative thinking, collaboration, and research abilities. In particular, teaching students in grades 1-4 of general secondary education using textbooks developed based on advanced foreign experience is of crucial importance [7].

Psychological and Pedagogical Essence of Concepts

Firstly, education is a conscious activity oriented toward acquiring knowledge through interaction between the teacher and students. Its main objectives include:

- a) Providing students with a system of knowledge determined by occupational standards and state educational standards;
- b) Developing students' logical thinking skills through the teaching of mathematical knowledge.

The psychological process called cognition involves moving from direct observation to abstract thinking, and then to practical application. Academician Yu.M. Kolyagin emphasized that "thinking is the active reflection of objective reality in human consciousness" [5]. Logical reasoning (thinking) is expressed through a certain system of scientific concepts. Any logical knowledge begins with sensory perception, which is why objects in the studied mathematical context are first perceived, then understood and imagined from an abstract perspective. Aristotle defined logic as "the science that determines unknown knowledge from known knowledge" and "distinguishes true reasoning from false reasoning." Based on this, mathematical logic studies reasoning using mathematical methods [5].

Teaching Methodology: Concept-Based Learning

In the methodology for developing oral speech and thinking in primary school students, a new approach called "concept-based learning" has been introduced. Key definitions are:

1. Key (core) word – a term that is central to the text's main content and is repeated several times (considering all possible synonyms).
2. Key (core) sentence – a phrase containing one or more key words.
3. Key phrase – a sentence that contains two or more key words or key sentences.

Key words can be categorized as:

1. Words that represent the general meaning of the text.
2. Words that represent specific sections of the text.
3. Words that represent the meaning of individual sentences.

The key words method emphasizes:

- Identifying key words and determining their specific meaning in the text.
- Considering that key words may have multiple meanings and understanding which meaning the author intends.

Key words are important for both the author and the student and require study through:

- Identification of key words,
- Determining their meaning in the text,
- Interpreting the concepts using dictionaries, encyclopedias, and reference materials.

The key concepts method helps children study larger texts effectively.

1. Key words are the most important words at the beginning of a text. Remembering them allows the student to immediately recall the main idea of the text.
2. While reading the introduction, one or two key words are selected. These selected words are written down in the correct sequence, and questions are created based on them. Then, the two key words are linked through questions, forming a chain. This chain is written down and studied. When retelling the text, students rely on this chain.

The state of key concepts in textbooks taught in primary grades has been studied and analyzed. Based on this, in the dissertation, a didactic model for teaching key concepts in primary grades was developed, taking into account the analysis of concepts in the third-grade Ona tili

(Mother Tongue) textbooks by M. Khudoyberganova and M. Mukhtorova (2005), as well as by S. Fuzailov and M. Khudoyberganova (2008).

Initial Classification of Concepts

In the school mathematics course, the simplest concepts that are not formally defined are conditionally accepted. For example:

- In arithmetic, the concepts of number and addition are considered undefined concepts.
- In geometry, concepts such as plane, point, distance, and straight line are considered undefined.

These basic concepts are then used to define other mathematical concepts. When defining concepts, the content of each concept is provided, meaning its main characteristics or essential features are enumerated.

Theoretical Foundations

The study of third-grade mathematics textbooks was approached in three directions:

1. First direction: M.I. Moro, M.A. Bantova, A.S. Pchylko's third-grade mathematics textbook (1970).
2. Second direction: N.U. Bikbayeva, Ye. Yangabayev's third-grade textbook (2004).
3. Third direction: L. Orinboyeva et al., third-grade textbook (2022).

These directions differ not only in content but also in axiomatic structure and primary concepts. The above distinctions were provided to fully classify the research basis, as the study focuses on concepts in primary grade mathematics textbooks.

Comparative Analysis

A comparative analysis was conducted on six third-grade mathematics textbooks:

- M.I. Moro, M.A. Bantova, A.S. Pchylko (1970)
- N.U. Bikbayeva, Ye. Yangabayev (2004, 2010)
- S. Burkhanov, O. Khudoyorov, Q. Norqulova (2016, 2019)
- L. Orinboyeva et al. (2022)

Since these textbooks were published in different years, the approaches to structuring certain topics vary considerably.

- In the first three textbooks, the content and sequence of concepts are roughly the same, differing mainly in presentation style.
- The fourth and fifth textbooks are almost identical to each other but differ from earlier textbooks. These include more concepts, with several new ones added.
- The latest textbook (2022) follows the STEAM program, with topics reorganized into chapters and presented in a convenient format.

Observations on Concept Implementation

After introducing the main concepts, each textbook reflects its own view on the importance and role of mathematical concepts. For instance:

- The first three textbooks contain concepts appropriate for third-grade students.
- The fourth and fifth textbooks introduce more complex concepts, including combinatorics, logic problems, positional and non-positional numeral systems, true and false statements, perpendicularity, symmetry, angles, and circular diagrams.
- Diagrams were first presented in Moro, Bantova, and Pchylko (1970), illustrating concepts like height and weight measurement. However, these concepts were not included in the 2016–2019 textbooks.

- The concept of fractions existed in earlier textbooks, but decimal fractions were newly introduced in the 2022 textbook. Other new concepts include shape rotation, angle symmetry, spatial figures (pyramid, cone), and two-step or two-operation problems.

The 2022 textbook by L. Orinboyeva et al. also contains the concepts from the fourth and fifth textbooks, with topics organized into separate chapters for clarity.

All third-grade textbooks begin with a review of concepts taught in the second grade, starting with the concepts of addition and subtraction. Afterward, the concepts of multiplication and division are introduced.

- In the M.I. Moro, M.A. Bantova, A.S. Pchyolko (2004) third-grade textbook, these concepts are presented in a dynamic way: how the sum changes depending on a change in one addend, how the difference changes depending on a change in the subtrahend or minuend, and so on.
- In N.U. Bikbayeva and Ye. Yangabayev (2004) third-grade textbook, the concepts of addition, subtraction, multiplication, and division are introduced similarly.
- In the textbooks by S. Burkhanov, O. Khudoyorov, Q. Norqulova (2016 and 2019), the operations are described with slightly more complex terminology, such as adding two-digit numbers across columns, subtracting two-digit numbers across columns, subtracting from a number, subtracting a difference from a number, etc. These new formulations serve as novel concepts for third-grade students and help develop their logical thinking skills.

Regarding multi-digit numbers:

- In M.I. Moro et al., students learn increasing and decreasing numbers by 10, 100, 1000, rounding numbers, and numbering multi-digit numbers.
- In N.U. Bikbayeva and Ye. Yangabayev (2004), numbers are presented in tens, hundreds, and thousands.
- In O. Khudoyorov and Q. Norqulova (2016) and S. Burkhanov et al. (2019), students study three-digit numbers, forming numbers from hundreds, tens, and units, relationships between three-digit numbers, sums of the units, and comparing three-digit numbers.
- The 2022 textbook continues this approach in the same form.

Equations, inequalities, algebraic expressions are presented similarly in all textbooks.

Regarding fractions:

- In M.I. Moro et al., fractions are introduced in the traditional sense.
- In N.U. Bikbayeva and Ye. Yangabayev (2004), fractions are introduced as parts or portions.
- In O. Khudoyorov and Q. Norqulova (2016) and S. Burkhanov et al. (2019), the concept of fractions is not included.
- In the new 2022 textbook, a separate chapter on fractions is provided. This chapter includes concepts of fractions, fractions with the same denominator, addition and subtraction of fractions, and comparisons, introducing several new mathematical concepts for third-grade students.

Units of measurement including length, weight, and time are presented in all textbooks. However, only in the 2022 textbook are the units of measurement given as a separate chapter. This chapter also includes STEAM tasks related to units of measurement and explores relationships between quantities.

Geometric shapes and concepts are also presented in all textbooks:

- In M.I. Moro et al., N.U. Bikbayeva and Ye. Yangabayev (2004), and O. Khudoyorov, Q. Norqulova (2016) third-grade textbooks, simple geometric shapes such as triangles and quadrilaterals are introduced.
- In S. Burkhanov, O. Khudoyorov, Q. Norqulova (2019), more complex shapes are introduced, including 3D figures such as pyramids, cones, and concepts of angle symmetry.
- In the 2022 textbook, geometric shapes are organized in a separate chapter, which includes both simple and 3D shapes, along with STEAM tasks related to geometry.

Conclusion

In primary school, teaching key concepts is crucial for developing students' oral communication and thinking skills. Based on the analyses mentioned above, teachers can organize lessons by applying modern educational technologies and student-centered teaching approaches.

The role of a primary school teacher is to develop students' independent logical thinking while fostering curiosity about the principles of learning.

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